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Research Article

**A STUDY ON THE PATIENTS SATISFACTION AND
EXPERIENCES FROM THE SURGICAL OUT PATIENT
DEPARTMENT OF A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL**¹Dr. Sana Ijaz, ²Dr. Ayesha Amin Cheema, ²Dr. Iqra Javaid¹Rawalpindi Medical College, Rawalpindi²CMH Lahore Medical College and Institute of Dentistry, Lahore**Abstract:**

Objective: The aim of this research is to find out the satisfaction and experience of the patient from the OPD of surgical department of a Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi.

Methodology: The research was carried out in surgical Out Patient Department of a Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi. This research work was carried out in the first three months of the year 2017. The patients were interrogated about the common state of the Out Patient Department, management methods, response duration, checkups time, and behaviour of doctors, their skilfulness, their contents and suggestion to other patients disregarding their social and areas information.

Results: Interview of four hundred and ninety patients was carried out after getting their willing for this research. More than seventy five percent patients were satisfied with the excellent ambience (including management methods, the behaviour of reception staff and waiting rooms) of Out Patient Department but only sixty four patients said that the sign of surgical Out Patient Department was visible. The average waiting duration was a 47.47 ± 15.29 minute (from fifteen minutes to one hundred and fifty minutes). About 301 patients were checked and their treatment recommended by the Residents and one hundred and eighty-nine patients got their treatment from Consultants. The average time of consultation was 6.03 ± 3.34 minutes (from two minutes to twenty minutes). Two hundred and forty-six patients viewed that the consultation duration was sufficient. Two hundred and eighty-seven patients willing were taken before the assessment but the solitude of the patients was kept while assessing three hundred and six patients. About 65 patients have to suffer succeeding problem of visit with the other departments. Ninety-seven percent patients viewed that they will make use of the Out Patient Department further and four hundred and sixty-one patients viewed that they will advice other to use it.

Conclusion: Generally, patient's know-how and contentment from surgical Out Patient Department was from fair to good. We highlighted many points for the betterments of many areas that are able to increase the quality of work and the contentment of the patients.

Keywords: OPD, Contentment, Patients, Consultants, Residents, know-how.

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INTRODUCTION:

The objective of healthcare squad is to give the patients with best advice with complete care. A large number of patients think visit to the hospital a complete fearful and new thing. The contact between staff of hospital and patients is a normal thing for hospital staff. The concentration, behaviour and data provided by the hospital staff are necessary for the patients [1]. Contentment is of the vital result for the health care [2]. Who has capability to decide the standards of a health care department – the attendants, staff nurses, medical assistants, administration staff or doctors? Medical care in the health care centre is defined by all of these but attendants or patients are most important participants to define this category.

Patients always need special care and attention. Therefore, the contentment of the patients is one of the most vital models for evaluating the QOC (quality of care) in OPD [3]. There are a low number of research works in Iran [5] and Pakistan [4] about the evaluation of the contentment of the patients in various aspects in patient, day case operation contentment [6] but partial general information is existing about the patients with experience of OPD and about their contentment.

METHODOLOGY:

This research work was carried out in surgical OPD of a Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi visited by the patients of Rawalpindi but also visited by the people of the surrounding areas. A form was created to gather the information by doctors who are not working in the Out Patient Department to reduce the prejudice. Patients are asked few questions about the

state of Out Patient Department, management methods, waiting duration, the behaviour of doctors and approval to other by patients disregarding their social economic and geographical status.

Participants were interrogated about the general contentment with the Out Patient Department in arrangement of ten point scale of anchored numerical. In that scale, digit one shows no satisfaction and digit ten shows extreme satisfaction of the patients. SPSS software version ten was used for the analysis of collected information. Variables were analyzed by the use of descriptive statistics.

RESULTS:

About 490 patients were interrogated while visiting the surgical Out Patient Department of a Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi. Verbal consent was taken from all the participants. This research work was carried out in the first three months of the year 2017. The average age of the participants was $45. \pm 13.52$ years from twelve years to eighty five years. The participants who were getting treatment from the surgical Out Patient Department for the very first time were 397. Profile based on the Demographic model is described in Table-1. More than seventy five participants were satisfied from the air of OPD. Only sixty four patients viewed that the sign of Out Patient Department was obviously observable. The average duration of waiting was 47.47 ± 15.29 minutes. The range of average duration of waiting time was fifteen minutes to two hours and thirty minutes. About 301 patients were checked and treatment recommended by the Residents and one hundred and eighty-nine patients got their treatment from Consultants.

Table-I: Demographic profile of the patient attending surgical OPD

Variable	n (%)
Age (years)	
<36	28 (25.7)
36-50	185 (37.8)
>50	179 (36.7)
Gender	
Male	294 (60)
Female	196 (40)
Visit	
First	397 (81)
Subsequent	93 (19)

The average duration of consultation was 6.03 ± 3.34 minutes. The range of average consultation time was two minutes to twenty minutes. Two hundred and forty six patients viewed that this time was sufficient. Two hundred and eighty-seven patients willing were taken before the assessment but the solitude of the patients was kept while assessing three hundred and six patients as described in Table-2. The surgical OPD will be used in future by 473 participants and four hundred and sixty one participants viewed that they will give advice others to visit it as mentioned in Table-2.

Table-II: Results of the questionnaire about experiences of Surgical OPD	
Question	n (%)
Inside the hospital the surgical OPD sign was clearly visible	64 (13.1)
Administrative procedures fast and easy	413 (84.3)
Pleasantness and availability of receptionist	401 (81.8)
Waiting room environment was pleasant	378 (77.1)
Is waiting time acceptable	392 (80.0)
Consultation by	
Resident	301 (61.4)
Consultant	189 (38.6)
Consultation time was adequate	246 (50.2)
Doctor was welcoming	255 (52.0)
Doctor took interest in you	311 (63.4)
Doctor examined carefully	462 (94.3)
Consent was taken before examination	287 (58.6)
Took care of your privacy	306 (62.4)
Explained what doctor was doing while examining	71 (14.5)

Warned about the side effects of the treatment	62 (12.7)
Your were explained about the decisions	322 (65.7)
You got the information you wanted	432 (88.2)
Agree with Doctor's instruction	479 (97.8)
Faced subsequent visit problem with other units	65 (13.2)
Would reutilize service in future	473 (96.5)
Recommend to others	461 (94.1)

DISCUSSION:

The know-how and the contentment of the patients in a health care centre is the most important service [2]. It is just like marketing. It has become a side tool for the recuperating the value of the health service. Sufferer's fulfilment is very vital for the best treatment results. They medical results are the results linked with the giver and not with the patients [1]. This research work described the fair experience of patients with the hospital stall and general air of atmosphere of Out Patient Atmosphere, staff skilfulness but ethical concerns were missing like no willing from many participants before start of work. The staffs are working for long duration in hospitals which make them insensible to the sufferings and wariness of the patients which is a natural thing. There is no compulsion on the behaviour of the staff in our medical hospitals [3]. The doctors were not giving much importance in taking willing, ensuring their fortitude, explanation of the disease and the side effects of the treatment as described in Table-2. All these aspects are the results of less time available in Out Patient Department, high amount of patients and fewer amounts of doctors. Each doctor checks about forty patients in only four hours. Most of the participants were getting complete information about their disease even when doctors were not able to give much time to the participants. This factor shows the good quality of our doctors which required being welcomed.

This research work concluded that a large quantity of the patients was satisfied. Thomas from UK reported that ninety two percent patients satisfied from their visit. This research work also proved that the medical staffs play a most vital role in the contentment of the patients [7]. Italians [8, 9] and UK [10] research works concluded the positive and negative points of hospital service while examining the contentment of the patients. They also tried to overcome the negative points to increase the satisfaction of the patients.

Lu SN [11] concluded that waiting time spent by the patients was 39.8 ± 42.9 minutes. More than fifty five percent patients had to spend more than 1 hour waiting which is too much. As the rate of visit was increasing by the patients, patients were in favour of the behaviour of doctors and their skilfulness which is most important aspect of the contentment of patients. There is a disparity in the attention paid by the medical staff to the patients in their early and latter visits [13]. Therefore, most of the patients were satisfied from management methods and air of the OPD but not from the skilfulness of the doctors because most of the participants were visiting OPD for the very first time. Six surgical units were

working in Benazir Bhutto Hospital Rawalpindi. Out Patient Department was run once in a week by each surgical unit. One patient was seen by same particular unit in which participant was examined on the very first day. This procedure was not confirmed to the patients who made difficulty for them. Sixty five patients from this research work faced his problem. Most of the participants will visit OPD in future and advise other to visit it.

CONCLUSION:

Generally, the contentment and experiences of the participants in this research work in the OPD was good. We gave many areas which were in need of improvement for increasing the quality of work and contentment of the patients.

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